

INDIAN AEROSPACE AND DEFENCE SECTOR AND ITS LINKAGES WITH ACADEMIA, IN PARTICULARLY ELECTRONICS AND TELECOMMUNICATION ENGINEERING: A DISCUSSION

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ABSTRACT

India's need for defence equipments and procurement of it is growing every year. The Indian government has set the defence production target at USD 25.00 billion by 2025 (including USD 5 billion from exports by 2025). In order to achieve this, India needs public and private partnership model in defence equipment manufacturing. In Aerospace and defence manufacturing, Electronics and Telecommunication plays a vital role. There is an opportunity of Rs. 3,30,000 Cr. of total electronics and telecommunication emerge by taking into consideration the requirements of Aerospace and defence sector in next 10 to 15 years. In order to achieve Atma-Nirbhar Bharat Mission, India needs to invest and build capabilities in Aerospace and defence manufacturing. It can be done by creating soft and hard infrastructure. The hard infrastructure is represented by existing defence public sector undertakings and some of the private sector companies. Under the Make in India Initiative, the government of India is encouraging the private investments in the defence sector, and it has set up seven new companies in year 2021 to attain the future defence needs. The soft infrastructure for the sector would comprise of intellectual capacity building, R & D and innovation. This discussion paper highlights the need of academia and defence sector linkages and proposes suggestions to link existing curriculum of related branches of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering vis-à-vis with Indian Defence Sector.

INTRODUCTION

According to the World Bank¹, India has been on a remarkable development journey since 1947. Currently Indian Economy has attained lower middle-income status from initially low-income nation. The current economic size of India is around 3 trillion United States Dollar (USD) and home to 1.3 billion people. Indian Per Capita GDP (Gross Domestic Product) is USD 6,121 with Human Development Index of 0.49.

India has 15,106 kilometers of land borders and a coastline of about 7,516 kilometers. Only 5 out of 29 Indian states have no international border or coastal line. Those long borders are shared with seven countries China, Pakistan, Bhutan, Myanmar, Afghanistan, Nepal and Bangladesh. Such extensive and porous borders run through different kinds of terrain, including mountains, hills, plains, valleys, forest, desert and swamp, and are sometimes difficult to monitor, especially at a time when territorial disputes and security troubles still plague parts of the Indian borderline.²

India's coastline measures 7,517 kilometers in length; of this distance, 5,423 kilometers belong to peninsular India and 2,094 kilometers to the Andaman, Nicobar, and Lakshadweep island chains.³

This complex situation is aggravated further as India's maritime boundaries are shared with seven countries Pakistan, Maldives, Sri Lanka, Indonesia, Thailand, Myanmar and Bangladesh.

Since Independence, India is constantly facing trouble at the Western and North Western Sector front and perennial border dispute with China on North East side as well as on the high altitude Ladakh sector.

Adam Smith justified the defence expenses as a first duty of a government (Dutta and Sharma 2005)⁴ and Indian Government is no exception.

Though there are some negative effects on the Defence Sector spending such as effecting the growth of other sectors of economy and less funds allocation for other social-economic goals, the need for defence sector funding increased manifold during last few decades due to turbulent world geo-political scenarios.

India with its uncanny neighbors has fought three Major Wars (China 1962, Pakistan 1965 & 1971) and one Minor war (Pakistan Kargil- 1999) apart from many incidences happening at the border areas. In order to protect its boundaries, India spent heavy amount on the defence expenditure. In the financial year 2021-22, the Indian government has allocated a budget of Rs. 4,78,196 Cr. of defence expenditure which is 13.73 per cent of the total central government expenditure and 2.15 percent of GDP for the year 2021-22.

The capital budget meant for acquiring new military systems and weapons stands at 25 per cent of the total capital expenditure. In order to maintain the peace, such cost must be borne by the Economy. According to the

SIPRI (Stockholm International Peace Research Institute), the five largest arms exporters during 2016–20 were the United States, Russia, France, Germany and China while the five largest arms importers were Saudi Arabia, India, Egypt, Australia and China.

The top five importers together received 36 per cent of all imports of major arms. In order to modernize its armed forces and reduce dependency over external dependence for defence procurement, several initiatives have been taken by the Indian government to encourage 'Make in India' activities via policy support initiatives. Indian companies were awarded defence contracts worth USD 37 billion during 2016-19, India plans to bring down its defence equipment import bill by at least USD 2 billion by 2022 so to encourage the local manufacturers. To attract foreign investment into defence manufacturing, the Indian government has announced a slew of measures including raising the cap on foreign investment from 49% to 74%. Indian Government formulated the 'Defence Production and Export Promotion Policy 2020' to provide impetus to self-reliance in defence manufacturing under the 'AatmaNirbhar Bharat' scheme. To encourage more participation from start-ups and micro, small & medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Defence Research & Development (R&D) in achieving the 'AatmaNirbhar Bharat' goal, the Defence Minister Mr. Rajnath Singh released a new version of 'Defence Research and Development Organisation (DRDO) Procurement Manual 2020' on October 20, 2020.

India's defence manufacturing sector recorded increased production to USD 10.9 billion in FY21, from USD 10.7 billion in FY20. The Indian government has set the defence production target at USD 25.00 billion by 2025 (including USD 5 billion from exports by 2025).

There are plans to establish new infrastructure including a defence park in Kerala to manufacture defence equipment for the armed forces. In July 2021, the Karnataka government announced the signing of Memoranda of Understanding (MOUs) with 23 companies from various sectors, including electric vehicles, data centres, aerospace, and defence in order to attract investments worth over Rs. 28,000 Cr. (USD 3.77 billion) and create nearly 15,000 direct jobs.

This discussion paper exploratory in nature is based upon the secondary data to highlight the contribution of Electronics Industry in Indian Defence Manufacturing and explores the possibility of future linkages of Academia with Aerospace and Defence Electronics Sector through *Make in India* mission so to achieve *AatmaNirbhar Bharat* goal in the Aerospace & Defence sector manufacturing.

1. OVERVIEW OF DEFENCE AND AEROSPACE SECTOR

The Indian Defence Industry sector, which was previously reserved for the public sector, was opened up to 100% for Indian private sector participation in May, 2001. As on date, 333 Private companies have been issued a total of 539 Industrial Licenses. Out of these, 110 companies have reported commencement of production.⁵

In order to give a lift to development of innovative defence technology and support a growing Startup base in the country, Ministry of Defence has earmarked Rs.1000 Cr. during 2021 – 22 for the procurement from the Innovation in Defence Excellence - *IDEX* Startups. These efforts aim to benefit 300 new Startups for innovative design and development in defence sector. Aiming for self-reliance in defence production, the seven new government-owned defence companies carved out of the Ordnance Factory Board (OFB) have already been given orders worth Rs. 65,000 Cr. The seven new Defence companies are: Munitions India Limited (MIL), Armoured Vehicles Nigam Limited (AVANI), Advanced Weapons and Equipment India Limited (AWE India), Troop Comforts Limited (TCL) (Troop Comfort Items), Yantra India Limited (YIL), India Optel Limited (IOL) and Gliders India Limited (GIL). These companies will be involved in production of defence equipment and material including ammunition, gun systems, and armored vehicles.⁶ India is the 7th largest Aerospace and Defence (A&D) market globally. The Total Defence Electronics market in India is USD 74 Billion in over next 10-14 years. The indigenous manufacturing base, historically built around DPSUs (Defence Public Sector Undertakings) and Ordnance Factories is only now evolving with private sector players focusing on setting up meaningfully sized and competent facilities.⁷ As the Aerospace and Defence industry evolves, the key impact is in terms of greater capability in platforms – a significant portion of this comes from electronics. Hence electronics in Indian Aerospace and Defence industrial plan is the critical center-piece that needs addressal. The challenge is compounded by the historically limited industrial base addressing electronics. In the world's top 100 defence equipment manufacturers, only two Indian companies namely Hindustan Aeronautics Limited and Bharat Electronics Limited make it to that list as against seven Chinese and fifty American companies.⁸

According to SIPRI, American defense firms are the indisputable leaders of the world's USD 398 billion arms sales industry in 2017. The ever rising geo-political tensions will increase this number further. India can not only become self-reliant but can be net exporter of Aerospace and defence equipment's in coming years looking at its capacity in this field.

Table 1: Countries and Number of Companies from it in TOP 100 Defence Equipment Manufacturing

Sr. Nos.	Country	Number of Companies from the Defence Manufacturing in TOP 100
1	USA	50
2	China	7
3	UK	7
4	France	5
5	Japan	3
6	Israel	3
7	Germany	2
8	Russia	2
9	India	2
10	Others	19
	Total	100

Source : <http://people.defensenews.com/top-100/>

As indicated earlier India's defence equipment spending as well aerospace spending is going up. This fact also highlights that the Hindustan Aeronautics Limited earn around 3.24 Billion USD as Revenue and 93% of it is from defence equipment's. The Bharat Electronics earn revenue of 1.91 Billion USD and 75 % of it from the sale of defence equipment's.

This potentially big market must be supported by the soft and hard infrastructure. Currently India is expanding the hard infrastructure as it has added seven new defence companies from the public sector to the existing nine Public Sector Undertakings (PSUs)

Table 2 : Indian PSUs in the Defence Equipment Manufacturing

Sr. Nos.	Existing Defence Companies PSU's with year of incorporation	Newly Set-Up PSUs (2021)
1	HINDUSTAN AERONAUTICS LIMITED (1950)	Munitions India Limited
2	BHARAT ELECTRONICS LIMITED (1954)	Armoured Vehicles Nigam Limited
3	BHARAT DYNAMICS LIMITED (1970)	Advanced Weapons and Equipment India Limited
4	BEML LIMITED (1964)	Troop Comforts Limited
5	MISHRA DHATU NIGAM LIMITED (1973)	Yantra India Limited
6	MAZAGON DOCK SHIPBUILDERS LIMITED (1934)	India Optel Limited
7	GARDEN REACH SHIPBUILDERS AND ENGINEERS LIMITED (1884)	Gliders India Limited
8	GOA SHIPYARD LIMITED (1957)	
9	HINDUSTAN SHIPYARD LIMITED (1941)	

2. ROLE OF ELECTRONICS AND TELECOMMUNICATION IN DEFENCE SECTOR

Electronics and Electronic systems are integral part of the defence equipments. Electronics and Telecommunication provides the capabilities that are critical to the defence requirements in terms of precision, the effectiveness and lethality of the weapons system. The Scope for electronics in Indian Context originates across both standalone systems and sub- system levels for another system. The Defence Electronics, Platform Electronics and Data links are the most sought after sub -system levels. Electronics has always been an important element of the defence sector, enabling communications, intelligence gathering and navigation. Object detection system uses radio waves to determine range, angle or velocity of objects such as aircrafts, ships, missiles, and spacecraft. Radar is used for target detection, target location and finding friend or FOE. Jamming, Spoofing can be done electronically to mislead the enemy in target detection. SONAR is used for sound navigation and ranging. Electronic Attack (EA) is the strategic use of electromagnetic or directed energy weapons to attack enemy forces' electronic infrastructure with the intention of degrading or eliminating their combat capabilities.

Looking at the next 10-15 years horizon, an opportunity of Rs. 3,30,000 Cr. of total electronics emerge by taking into the consideration the requirements of three defence services.⁹

Table 3: Selected Indian Listed Companies (Private and Public) in the Defence Equipment Manufacturing

Sr. Nos.	Name of The Company	Net Sales In Rs. Cr	Net Profit in Rs. Cr
1	Hindustan Aeronautics Ltd.	22,742	3,234
2	Bharat Electronics Ltd.	14,108	2069
3	Mazagon Dock Shipbuilders Ltd.	4,049	479
4	BEML Ltd.	3,556	68
5	Cochin Shipyard Ltd.	2,818	608
6	Bharat Dynamics Ltd.	1,913	257
7	Garden Reach Shipbuilders & Engineers Ltd.	1,140	153
8	Mishra Dhatu Nigam Ltd.	813	166
9	MTAR Technologies Ltd.	246	46
10	Paras Defence and Space Technologies Ltd.	132	15
11	TAAL Enterprises Ltd.	104	31
12	Zen Technologies Ltd.	54	02
13	Taneja Aerospace and Aviation Ltd.	34	6

Source : www.moneycontrol.com

Table 4 : The World's Leading Space Research Organizations

Sr. Nos.	Name of the Space Research Organizations	Country	Annual Budget in USD millions (2018)
1	National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA)	U.S.A.	19,500
2	China National Space Administration	China	11,000
3	European Space Agency (ESA)	EU	6,300
4	Roscosmos State Corporation for Space Activities (Roscosmos)	Russia	3,300
5	Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA)	Japan	2,000
6	Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO)	India	1,500

Source : <https://www.statista.com/statistics/947300/leading-space-agencies-by-government-budget-worldwide/>

Indian Space and Research Programme is led by ISRO with many successful missions under its name. Current budget of ISRO is USD 1,900 million as of 2021. Antrix Corporation Limited was incorporated as a private limited company owned by Government of India in September 1992 as a Marketing arm of ISRO for promotion and commercial exploitation of space products, technical consultancy services and transfer of technologies developed by ISRO. Another major objective is to facilitate development of space related industrial capabilities in India.¹⁰

It offers expertise under

- SATCOM Services
- Ground System Services
- Spacecraft Testing Facility
- Spacecraft and Subsystems
- Mission Support System, and
- Remote Sensing Data and Services.¹¹

ISRO has Recognized the need for a broader academic interface with institutions across the country with a series of capacity building initiatives taken up to further strengthen the involvement of academia for ISRO

programs. Such initiatives could be termed as soft infrastructure so to accelerate the growth and reach of Aerospace-Defence electronics sector.

The Electronics also plays a key role in the Artificial Intelligence *AI*. The smart and adequate use of *AI* in armed forces would enhance the capabilities and effectiveness of all forces.

UAVs, drones and loiter munitions technology can be used for surveillance and reconnaissance. The small drones can be used in tactical operations by forces. It would help to provide real-time intelligence for tactical decision making by commanders.¹² Robotics, autonomous systems, *AI* have military utility. However, it's commercial and industrial utility goes into hundreds of billions. Development of the defence industry in this sector will also spur the modern commercial industry underpinned by these technologies.¹³

3. PROPOSED ACADEMIA – AEROSPACE, DEFENCE SECTOR LINKAGES

The soft infrastructure essential for the development of this sector in Indian context would be in terms of capacity building, R & D and innovation. This could be further developed with leveraging India's young technical talent pool. India has the largest number of engineers as well as the largest number of engineering education institutes and infrastructure in the world. As of 2021, India annually produces one million engineering graduates from 3500 engineering colleges.

Of the million engineering graduates produced every year, less than 5% of the engineers are produced by the pan-India national level autonomous institutes created by the acts of parliament, such as the Indian Institutes of Technology (IITs), National Institutes of Technology (NITs) and Indian Institutes of Information Technology (IIITs). The remaining over 90% of the engineering graduates are produced by the private and non-autonomous state level engineering education institutes. According to the Statista Research Department, in year 2019 around 6,31,370 students enrolled through-out India in the field of Electronics Engineering.¹⁴

This is the third largest discipline enrollment next to Computer Science and Mechanical Engineering

Such high number of enrollment and existing Engineering institutions makes India a cradle of talent pool which could be inter-linked with the growing Defence Electronics Industry. One of the problems faced by India's budding Engineers is that they are not employable.¹⁵

Only three per cent of engineer graduates in India get high-quality tech jobs with salary packages of Rs. 8,00,000 to 10,00,000 and over 80 per cent of these graduates end up pursuing non-technical careers due to lack of available employment opportunities.¹⁶

This problem needs immediate attention through strategic intervention. Such intervention could be possible by linking the Aerospace and Defence Electronics Industry with the existing curriculum of Electronics Engineering discipline. The experiential learning by the way of summer and live projects along with innovation labs in these Defence Electronics Fields will develop the fertile minds of young engineers which will make them not only employable but also remunerate enough to accept more challenges in the field. This would suffice the growing need of defence electronics manufacturing with multi facet benefits such as

- Channeling the innovative minds in the Defence Electronics sector
- Partially Solving the problem of Employability
- Building R & D Capabilities
- Bolstering the Industry Academia linkages
- Self Sufficiency in Defence Equipment Manufacturing, a step closer to *AatmaNirbhar Bharat*

4. CONCLUSIONS

The concept Paper illustrated the importance of Aerospace Defence Electronic sector in Indian Context. There would be many opportunities available for Indian Industry to participate in this over expanding segment. The Academia represented in terms Electronics & Telecommunication Engineering would be a vital cog in the wheel to support the hard infrastructure for this Industry. The interaction between the Academia and Aerospace Defence Electronics sector proves to be mutually beneficial with far reaching effects. In this light, this paper proposes to re-calibrate the syllabus of related branches of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering to incorporate the modern Technology and Tools which could be useful for the sustainability of Aerospace Defence Electronics sector in Indian Context.

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